

THE EFFECT OF FIBER ORIENTATION ON THE DYNAMIC MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF KEVLAR® FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

Jenny Z. Yu and Frank K. Ko
Fibrous Materials Research Laboratory
Department of Materials Engineering, Drexel University
Philadelphia, Pennsylvania

John W. Song
Fiber and Polymer Science Division, Science and Technology Directorate
U.S. Army Natick Research, Development & Engineering Center
Natick, Massachusetts

ABSTRACT

The dynamic mechanical behavior of Kevlar® fiber reinforced composites was characterized by generating the master curves of both flexural storage modulus and damping loss factor using the frequency-temperature superposition principle. To examine the effect of fiber orientations, four laminates layups were selected. The rank among the four laminates in terms of storage modulus was: [0] > [0/90] > [±45] > [90]. A opposite trend was obtained for their damping behavior. But the difference of the damping capability among these four diminishes as frequency increases. The stiffness of the Kevlar® composites increases dramatically with the increase of the frequency, especially for [0] laminate, while their damping loss factors approach a similar constant value as frequency increases irrespective of their fiber orientations and fiber volume fractions. This means that with Kevlar® fiber reinforced composites it is possible to achieve both high stiffness and moderate damping without trade-off.

1. INTRODUCTION

When viscoelastic materials are subjected to high frequency or high velocity impact, the stiffness of the materials increases dramatically, which resembles the behavior of viscoelastic material at low temperature[1, 2]. The ideal situation for designers to design a structure is to optimize both stiffness and damping at the same time. By selecting fibers with relatively larger damping such as aramid fiber as reinforcement, it is possible to achieve both high stiffness and high damping [3, 4]. A desirable level of impact energy absorption would be achieved when sufficient damping is superimposed with the increased stiffness at a high velocity impact. Therefore, a thorough understanding of dynamic mechanical properties such as storage modulus and damping properties over a wide range of frequencies is essential to optimize the materials as well as the structures of the composites.

In this study, the dynamic mechanical properties of the Kevlar® fiber reinforced composites, namely, E' , the storage modulus, E'' , the loss modulus and $\eta = \tan\delta = E''/E'$, the loss tangent which is also called damping loss factor under various frequencies, were estimated by generating the master curves of both flexural storage modulus and damping loss factor using the frequency-temperature superposition principle[5, 6, 7]. The effects of fiber orientation, fiber volume fraction on Kevlar® 29 fiber reinforced epoxy composites were examined.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MATERIALS

Kevlar® 29 fibers and Kevlar® 29 2x2 basket weave fabrics with 1500 denier yarn were used as reinforcements of the composites. The matrix material was Epon® resin 8132 and curing agent U. The composite specimens were fabricated by compression molding technique at room temperature. To examine the effect of fiber orientations, four laminate layups were selected, which included [0], [0/90], [± 45] and [90]. [0] and [90] were unidirectional composite. [0/90] and [± 45] were made of woven fabric composites. The effect of fiber volume fraction was studied with a series of unidirectional composites. A summary of the composite specimen is listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Details of the DMA Specimens

	Materials	Lay-up	Dimensions (LxWxH)(mm)	Fiber Volume Fraction V_f	Test Direction
1	Pure Epoxy	N/A	35.06x14.32x2.58	N/A	Longitudinal
2	Kevlar 29/Epoxy	Unidirectional	L1, L/h=19.02 55.54x12.67x2.92	50%	Longitudinal
3	Kevlar 29/Epoxy	Unidirectional	L2, L/h=11.90 35.58x12.49x2.99	50%	Longitudinal
4	Kevlar 29/Epoxy	Unidirectional	L3, L/h=4.16 12.03x12.70x2.89	50%	Longitudinal
5	Kevlar 29/Epoxy	Unidirectional	L/h=18.64 55.54x12.95x2.98	65%	Longitudinal
6	Kevlar 29/Epoxy	Unidirectional	L/h=11.29 55.54x12.30x4.92	50%	Transverse
7	Kevlar 29/Epoxy	Unidirectional	L/h=11.33 55.54x13.18x4.90	70%	Transverse
8	Kevlar 29/Epoxy	Basket Weave	L/h=11.94 55.54x13.16x4.65	50%	0/90
9	Kevlar 29/Epoxy	Basket Weave	L/h=11.82 55.54x13.06x4.70	50%	± 45

Note: L/h is the length to thickness ratio.

2.2 TESTING CONDITIONS

The composite samples were tested with a TA Instrument DMA-983. A fixed frequency multiplexing method (MULTZ) was used with test frequencies of 0.1, 0.32, 1.0 and 3.2 HZ. The test temperature range was from -100°C to 100°C with heating rate of 5°C/min and oscillation amplitude of 0.1 mm.

In order to estimate the behavior of fiber reinforced composites under high velocity impact such as ballistic impact which exceeds the frequency capability of the DMA tester, master curves for both storage modulus and damping loss factor ($\tan \delta$) were constructed using temperature-frequency superposition principle. All the master curves were generated with a reference temperature of 23°C.

K29 and K29B as legends of the specimens represent Kevlar® 29 fibers and Kevlar® 29 basket weave fabric, respectively. V50, V65 and V75 represent fiber volume fractions of 50%, 65% and 70%, respectively. L and T represent longitudinal and transverse test directions of unidirectional composites respectively.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 FIBER ORIENTATION EFFECT

The effects of fiber orientations on the flexural storage modulus E' of the materials are shown in Figure 1. It can be seen that for [0] laminate since all the fibers were aligned along the test direction, the composites demonstrate much higher storage modulus than [90] laminate in which all the fibers aligned perpendicular to the loading direction. For the evaluated composites, a ten-fold difference in the storage modulus between the longitudinal and transverse directions is obtained. Figure 1 also shows the storage modulus vs. frequency spectra for [0/90] and $[\pm 45]$ laminate composites. It clearly shows that since the [0/90] laminate has more fibers aligned along the test direction than $[\pm 45]$ laminate does, it demonstrates higher values of storage modulus throughout the frequency range although they have the same total fiber volume fraction of 50%. Under high velocity impact, such as ballistic impact, the velocity corresponds to 10^5 HZ in frequency [6]. To maximize the ballistic impact energy absorption of the composites, it is important to examine the behavior of the materials at this frequency. Figure 2(a) depicts the effect of fiber orientation on the storage moduli of the composites at frequency of 10^5 HZ and 0.1 HZ. It is evident from Figure 2(a) that the composites show significant frequency dependent properties. In Figure 2(b), the modulus value in the y axis has been normalized by the corresponding E' of [0] laminate. It clearly shows that the evaluated materials rank in a descending order by the configurations [0], [0/90], $[\pm 45]$ and [90]. The smallest value is demonstrated by [90] laminate where the performance appears to be more influenced by matrix properties than fiber properties.

Fig. 1 Comparison of the Effect of the Fiber Orientations on Storage Modulus of the Composites

Figure 2 (a) Effect of the Fiber Orientations on Storage Modulus of the Composites at the Frequency of 0.1 HZ and 10⁵ HZ

Figure 2 (b) Effect of the Fiber Orientations on Storage Modulus of the Composites at the Frequency of 10⁵ HZ

The effects of fiber orientation on the damping properties of the materials are shown in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 3 exhibits the damping loss factor variation of the four different laminates with frequency. Figure 4 shows the comparison of the damping peak values and the damping values at the frequency of 10⁵ HZ for the four evaluated laminates. It can be seen from Figure 3 that the loss factor of [90] laminate is more than twice that of [0] laminate within the transition range, and [0/90] and [±45] laminates fall in between. Figure 4 depicts that neat matrix shows almost 100% damping value at peak, [90] laminate shows a second highest peak value of 47%, along with 24% for [±45], 20% for [0/90] and 18% for [0] laminate. But, it can be seen that, from Figures 3 and 4, the loss factor differences among them are getting smaller and smaller with the increase of the frequency. When the frequency is equal to 10⁵ HZ, the damping values of all the four materials are less than 4%. Figures 4 and 2 demonstrate an opposite trend in the damping loss factor and the storage moduli. A noticeable shifts of the damping peak positions can be observed from Figure 3. It seems less stiffer composites tend to peak their damping factor at a relative higher frequency. Further study is needed on the factors which affect the position of the damping peak.

Fig. 3 Comparison of the Effect of the Fiber Orientations on the Damping Loss Factor of the Composites

Figure 4 Effect of the Fiber Orientations on Damping Loss Factors of the Composites at Different Frequencies

3.2 FIBER VOLUME FRACTION EFFECT ON DYNAMIC PROPERTIES OF THE COMPOSITES

The effects of fiber volume fraction on the storage modulus of Kevlar 29 fiber reinforced composites are shown in Fig. 5 (a). It can be seen that the storage moduli of the unidirectional composites increase as the fiber volume fraction increases. The difference in storage modulus between unidirectional composites with 65% and 50% fiber volume fractions is about 5 to 6 GPa through the whole frequency range. Fig. 5 (b) shows the effect of fiber volume fraction on the longitudinal dynamic loss factor. It exhibits the loss factor is inversely proportional to the increase of the fiber volume fraction. At the peak position, the composite with 50% fiber volume fraction has a loss factor of 17.91%, but the one with 65% fiber volume fraction only has a peak loss factor of 13.45%, reduced by 4.46%. However, as frequency increases, the difference reduces gradually, and eventually becomes negligible.

Fig. 5 Effect of Fiber Volume Fraction on (a) the Storage Modulus (b) on the Damping Loss Factor of the Unidirectional Composites When Tested along the Longitudinal Direction(L), $V_f=65\%$ (V65) vs. $V_f=50\%$ (V50).

On the other hand, the effect of fiber volume fraction on the unidirectional composites tested in the transverse direction differs significantly from that tested along the longitudinal direction. Figure 6 (a) displays E' vs. frequency curves for unidirectional composites with 50% fiber volume fraction and 70% fiber volume fraction, and pure matrix. The matrix shows higher E' than the composites at low frequency range. The 50% fiber volume fraction composite exhibits a higher E' value than the 70% composite. In the transverse testing configuration, the reinforced fibers were placed in a direction perpendicular to the principle loading direction; thus, the performance of the composite was influenced by matrix properties rather than fiber properties. As fiber volume fraction increases, the total number of imperfect fiber matrix interface increase, in other words, more weak links exist in the composites having a higher fiber volume fraction. So one of the major reasons which cause the lower transverse storage modulus value of the composites is the weak link effect.

The effect of fiber volume fraction on the transverse dynamic loss factor is shown in Figure 6 (b). The loss factor is inversely proportional to the fiber volume fraction. At the peak position, pure matrix shows almost 100% damping, while the composite with 50% fiber volume fraction has a loss factor of 47.11% and the one with 70% fiber volume fraction has a peak loss factor of 38.35%. Damping comes mainly from the contributions of the matrix material around the transition range, although the imperfect interfaces between fiber and matrix also contribute to the total energy dissipation, it appears that the contribution of the matrix viscoelastic damping is much more significant than that of the interfacial damping (Fig. 6 (b)). With the increase of frequency, the effect of fiber volume fractions decreases, and eventually becomes negligible. Again, similar to Figure 3, a noticeable shifts of the damping peak position can be observed from Figure 6 (b), less stiffer composites as evidenced by Figure 6 (a) show peaks at a higher frequency.

Fig. 6 Effect of Fiber Volume Fraction on (a) the Storage Modulus and (b) the Damping Loss Factor of the Unidirectional Composites When Tested along the Transverse Direction(T), $V_f=70\%$ (V70) vs. $V_f=50\%$ (V50).

4. SUMMARY

The fiber orientation effects of the composites were studied by selecting four different laminate layups including [0], [90], [0/90] and $[\pm 45]$. The storage modulus of the evaluated materials were ranked in a descending order by the configurations: [0], [0/90], $[\pm 45]$, and [90]. As expected, the composites with fibers aligned along the testing direction, such as the [0] configuration, demonstrated the highest storage modulus and the composites with no fiber aligned along the testing direction, such as [90], show the least. The storage modulus of the composites with some fibers aligned along the testing direction, i.e. [0/90] and $[\pm 45]$ were somewhere between. For the damping properties, the transverse loss factor of the unidirectional composites doubles their longitudinal loss factor around the transition range. The ranks among the four configurations [0], [0/90], $[\pm 45]$ and [90] in terms of their damping capabilities inverse their ranks in terms of the storage modulus. But the difference of the loss factor among these materials diminishes as frequency increases. The effect of fiber volume fraction was pronounced. The modulus of the composites increase with the increase of the total amount of the fibers aligned along the test direction. The longitudinal storage modulus of the unidirectional composites with 65% fiber volume fraction is 5 to 6 GPa higher than that of the composite with only 50% fiber volume fraction, while the damping loss factor is inversely proportional to the increase of the fiber volume fraction. On the other hand, the effect of fiber volume fraction on the transverse storage modulus is not significant at all, but the transverse damping loss factor is sensitive to the fiber volume fraction change, which is inversely proportional to the increase of the fiber volume fraction.

It can be concluded that damping and stiffness behave in opposite manners around their transition range. But, after the transition range, the stiffness of the Kevlar® composites increases dramatically with the increase of the frequency, especially for [0] configuration, while their damping loss factors approach a similar constant value as frequency increases irrespective of their fiber orientations and fiber volume fractions. This means that with Kevlar® fiber reinforced composites it is possible to achieve both high stiffness and moderate damping without trade-off.

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